

**An Innovation Searching for Boosting the Romania & Portugal Nations
etc. GDP comparison Analysis on Scientist Publishing Papers at High
Impact Factor Journal Sustainably**

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ABSTRACT: The education course will affect the futural industries development on the views of affording more competitive talent like scientist who would be completing his expertise drill in university for the sake of acquiring good job after he graduates from university. With meeting the futural industries development they need to be educated the high-tech knowledge so that he will utilize the relevant one to proceed his research and development work independently and collaboratively. Thereby he need to communicate with others fluently and skillfully or he will meet the autism that affects him to complete the task smoothly. Our teacher can find that fact and help him to conquer the difficulty for the declining sacrifice early so that he may continue to graduate from university and enter society and find good job for him to burden a new task in R &D department dedicated to the society responsibility. So that our society can make the continual development from easy to difficulty and from zero to 1,000 attained a complicate situation and create the new-high-tech

product continuously with artificial intelligence algorithm under big-language modal environment. Therefore, we need more qualified scientist to participate the innovation product research and development sustainably for the sake of commonly progressing our new products to be exhibit in market like cafe & restaurant to move the coffee & cuisine conveniently. We can only order the cuisine through touching small ordering screen to choose what to need, so simple. Thereby the comfortable service will be provided by that artificial intelligence moving robot according to the demand of customers. If they can speak simple greet language it is so good with language model to assemble it for paying attention to their coming. So that there is so much robot etc. innovation product exhibition to make our life level step a higher hierarchical structure. We also join the robot making work and invent more their equipment to be convenient to others through our continually research work. We should aware we are to experience a new era working with robot, so we should also learn it and make some advice for improving their enhancement property. At the end the high-technology product like robot etc innovative ones will change the life mode ultimately that may be beneficial to improve the GDP value in some degree. Thereby we should continuously study and search for its futural widely usefulness with our scientist talents together who will put-in the commanding order into chip for it that will change the world through lately exhibiting robot heat. On the other side, the computer skill and technology will help to develop the live convenience and comfortability with plugging chip etc. integrated circuit designed through editing the computer language's function.

Keywords: *boosting GDP value increasement, Romania & Portugal Nations, Yugoslavia & Finland, innovation research, sustainably, publish papers*

1. Introduction

The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot

quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI(artificial intelligence), ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument

&device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~20]

2. Discussions

For the sake of welcoming the demand we should educate a lot of scientist and experts candidates from university department to college &institution one to take the high scholar degree for them to grasp one foreign language and skill to apply to futural requirement and practice. In university, the class with taking more practice education and experience and good teacher proceed the more competition teaching and theoretical and practical combination class to prepare for using after their graduate from college.

2.1 Ireland &Hubei province GDP comparison

The Ireland &Hubei province GDP would analyzed with 15~2 billion dollars accordingly exhibited the Ireland forwarder economy status with almost seven times variation between them in1978 in light of Figure 1. The y-y value might indicate 27% &18% recorded their more modest growth steps whilst the Hubei province remained little step.

Figure 1 The Austria &Denmark GDP analysis. [1]

2.3 Romania & Portugal GDP comparison

The Romania & Portugal GDP data would show 26~24 billion dollars accordingly explained their forwards economy status in Figure 2 in 1978. The y-y value might indicate 3% & 7% accordingly by them realized Portugal forward growth step.

Figure 2 The Romania & Portugal GDP analysis. [2]

At the end, the Romania & Portugal GDP data would show 11~6 billion dollars accordingly explained their forwards economy status in Figure 3 in 1967. The y-y value might indicate 11% & 10% accordingly by them realized forward growth step.

Figure 3 The Romania & Portugal GDP comparison

2.4 Yugoslavia & Finland GDP comparison

The Yugoslavia & Finland GDP data would show 412~9 billion dollars accordingly explained their forwards economy status in Figure 4 in 1967. The y-y value might indicate 5% & 0.5% accordingly by them realized forward growth step.

Figure 4 The Yugoslavia & Finland GDP comparison [3]

The Yugoslavia & Finland GDP data would show 44~40 billion dollars accordingly explained their forwards economy status in Figure 5 in 1978. The y-y value might indicate 6% & 11% accordingly by them realized forward growth step.

Figure 5 The Yugoslavia & Finland GDP comparison [3]

2.5 Sweden &Netherland GDP comparison

The Sweden &Netherland GDP data would show 107~159 billion dollars accordingly explained their forwards economy status in Figure 6 in 1978. The y-y value might indicate 7% &13% accordingly by them recorded forward growth step. In contrast, the Netherland retained higher GDP value &y-y value to express its forward prosperity.

Figure 6 The Sweden &Netherland GDP comparison.

2.6 Subject for the International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications

The IJERA Journal has its e-mail address of ijera.ad@gmail.com. As for researchers, International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications is ISO 3297:2007 certified open access and peer reviewed refereed international Journal. The IJERA invites articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of Engineering, Technology, Science and Mathematics. INDEXING: NASA Ads, ArXiv, ANED (American National Engineering Database), EBSCOHost, Cabell's Directory, DOAJ, NCBI (US National Library) etc. Therefore, the Impact factor of IJERA will be 6.185 with <http://www.ijera.com/impact-factor.html>. The IC Value (By Index Copernicus): 5.29. on the other side, the article notification will be within 1 days after Submission, whilst the publication (online) may be within 2 days. [21] So that we heartily hope all the authors around the world to submit their cherish papers to us, we will publish them in time.

Summarily, the enhancing GDP factors will include the high-technique products and its whole industrial chains and high-intelligence product that may influence the service business mostly. So we should increase those high-profit & high-tech skill for making more advance products so as to improve our service business level and quality & effectiveness at all. So that we should maintain and develop the tertiary industry continuously under controlling the second one. With the life quality enhancing continually the service one is about to wield its effectiveness presently and in futural long time, thereby we should follow up the changed situation and own independent capacity to master one outstanding skill to satisfy the futural request in advance.

3. Conclusions

The education course will affect the futural industries development on the views of affording more competitive talent like scientist who would be completing his expertise drill in university for the sake of acquiring good job after he graduates from university. With meeting the futural industries development they need to be educated the high-tech knowledge so that he will utilize the relevant one to proceed his research and development work independently and collaboratively. Thereby he need to communicate with others fluently and skillfully or he will meet the autism that affects him to complete the task smoothly. Our teacher can find that fact and help him to conquer the difficulty for the declining sacrifice early so that he may continue to graduate from university and enter society and find good job for him to burden a new task in R & D department dedicated to the society responsibility. So that our society can make the continual development from easy to difficulty and from zero to 1,000 attained a complicate situation and create the new-high-tech product continuously with artificial intelligence algorism under big-language modal environment. Therefore, we need more qualified scientist to participate the innovation product research and development sustainably for the sake of commonly progressing our new products to be exhibit in market like cafe & restaurant to move the coffee & cuisine conveniently. We can only order the cuisine through touching small ordering screen to choose what to need, so simple. Thereby the comfortable service will be provided by that artificial intelligence moving robot according to the

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Ethic Declarations

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest.

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